

Information System Analysis and Design

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Abstract— Information Systems are artificial systems consisting of components in organizations that can present information. A good information system can improve the performance of all activities in the company that is supported by careful and more secure data, as a result of which all activities can run more effectively. One of the parts according to this company that is crucial is the storage. The crucial thing in the warehouse is the recording of existing goods data. In this section there is a poor system where manual recording of data as a result can affect the emergence of errors. Therefore, it is necessary to design an information system data item so that the time needed to search for data is not long and simplify the flow of information. The design of these information systems goes through several stages starting with surveys within the company, identification problems, system analysis, model design and finally by designing information systems using databases and applications.

Index Terms—Data, Database, Design, Information System, Performance, System Analysis.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE effectiveness and efficiency of information systems is a key aspect. Which can determine the progress or decline of an organization. The organization of the manufacturing industry is inseparable from that thing. Effective information systems and properly implemented will affect management performance on the control of the production system in the manufacturing industry. However, the information system too complex and complicated can decrease the efficiency of the system production as a whole ^[1].

As the need increases company on the management of items who acts as a provider in the process production, demanding change in terms of system improvement. This condition in personal causes it to be done a Continuous Improvement on things improved management ^[2]. The company has its own way of control the internal information. Information it will be delivered based on the level leadership down to the top or the opposite is neatly arranged.

It has great regional potential it turned out to cause its own challenges. For the central government, even more so to local governments in doing management of the potential of the region aforementioned. Therefore, good analysis and design are needed in information systems in keeping up with the rapid

development of technology and work culture ^[3].

In Indonesia, intensive study of system integration quality management and information have not been done much. Industrial Baristand Padang is a government organization/forum below Industrial Research and Development Agency, Ministry Industry of the Republic of Indonesia. Baristand Padang Industry have a duty to carry out research /research activities and standardization and certification in the industry as a research and standardization forum in Indonesia ^[4].

II. LITERATUR REVIEW

This part contains the study literature that use in this article.

A. Information System

A system is a network based on interconnected mechanisms, gather together to do an activity or to complete if a specific target, the system can also it is defined as a collection of elements that interact with each other to achieving a specific goal. While the information is data that has been processed into a form it is more useful and more meaningful to those who accept. It can be concluded that the information system it's a system that's mutual, affiliated with each other, formed by human beings consisting of components in the organization to achieve the purpose is to present information ^[2].

A system is a group of elements that are integrated with the intention of the same in achieving a goal. Each system is designed to do something repeated or it routinely happens to achieve something purpose. A system has characteristics or the exclusive properties that characterize that it can be said as a system ^[3].

B. Information System Purpose

An information system is a one-aspect error necessary in an organization. Forward or backward the organization is represented by the effectiveness and efficiency of the system information used by the organization.

The general purposes of information systems include:

1. Provide information that can help the process management decision making;

2. Make it easier the implementation of daily operations; and
3. provide information worthy of outside the organization, especially regarding issues transparency of management ^[1].

C. Database

A database can be defined as a collection of data that integrated, organized and stored in a way so it can be taken back easily. Defines a database as a data set that computerized into information interconnected and organized and can be obtained in a quick and easy. The main function of the database is to provide information for its users ^[1].

Database in the system information is used as:

1. Place to store data and information;
2. Tools for processing data and providing reports related to data or information stored.

The data contained in the database must be integrated. Logically. Logical integration is called concept in the database. In addition to being integrated, the database must also be able to define storage location. Data and information it is stored in table form and is related to each other.

Hierarchy of data in a database starting from the highest order up to the lowest is ^[1]:

1. Database
2. File
3. Note
4. The Data Element.

Database design is the process that produces a detailed data model based on databases, database design involves selecting: columns for each table and how tables and columns interact with each other term. Database design can serve as an application based on the overall planning process, not just in the structure the database, but also the query and its form that has function becomes a part based on the database thoroughly in a database management system ^[5].

After identification of system components, then the steps next in the system design optimal information. Designing the proposed system needs to be done in order to get a better system. Data is expressed as a group based on table relationships. Relationship are 2-dimensional tables based on data who has a name. Every relationship contains a group by name columns and rows that have contents different. Structured relationship with it's good to have an interaction. Contains a minimum amount based on redundancies & allow wearer to enter, replace and delete lines without error or data inconsistency. MySQL is a medium or a vehicle to create a database ^[2].

III. DISCUSSION

This Part involve discussion section about this article.

A. Database Design

Good database design should minimize repetition of data and achieving data independence. Steps -steps of database design are ^[5]:

1. Determine the purpose of the database.
2. Gather and find all the necessary information. For example, the order number and product name.
3. Share the data that has been obtained into a table, then for any information in a subject or large entity.
4. Convert each information into a column and decide name information that should be stored in the table.
5. Specify the primary key, select the primary key of each table.
6. Set the relationship between tables.
7. Complete the plan and then analyze the plan.
8. Set the rules of normalization at the beginning of a sentence.

B. Weakness Before Information System

In warehousing systems before the existence of information systems it has some disadvantages such as ^[5]:

1. In terms of users do not know the spare parts in the warehouse there are or not, feel aggrieved because to do taking spare parts from the warehouse, no evidence spare parts from the user.
2. In terms of warehouses, warehouse people are easier to do data manipulation of spare part ordering data, spare part in, spare part out, stock spare part and fake bon. Warehouse people don't want to make spare part reports coming in and stock spare parts for reasons of many jobs and order spare parts from the user, so that warehouse people Reason not to have time to make a spare part report go in and stock spare parts. Warehouse people make recording spare parts out manually as written hands on books and sheets of paper, making them very vulnerable there was a recording error.
3. In terms of finance still make purchase orders in manual and difficulty in carrying out spare supervision part starting from report stock out, stock report, report receive item and user report.
4. In terms of admin has difficulty in doing spare parts in the warehouse.

C. Analysis Information System and Design

Information system design begins with redesign existing business processes. Application on the internet open opportunities for improved process efficiency, so that redesign is aimed at simplifying the process business. Business Process Diagram is used as a guide in the process of redesign. Although effective in shows business processes in outline, business process The diagram does not clearly show the interactions that occur between actor and system. The interaction is illustrated through use case diagram. Basically, the use case is used to

describe system functions, involvement and role of actors in that system ^[1].

Common components of the use case diagrams among others:

1. Actor, defined as a person or something outside the system that interacts with the system to doing certain jobs. The usual "stickman" symbol used to represent actors.
2. Use case. It is a function of a system unit that performs transfer of information and changes between actors or units. Deep use case diagram, use case represented in elliptical form the name of the use case.
3. Relationship, Describes the relationship between two or more actors with use case. The symbol of the relationship is usually a line with /no arrows.

IV. CONCLUSION

This part contains a conclusion from the article that has been discuss and analysis before.

An information system in general is a system that combines human activity and the use of technology to support management and operational activities. It refers to a relationship created based on human interaction, data, information, technology, and algorithms.

The purpose of information system development is to produce a product that contains a collection of information. A system of course involves various types and types of data that can be processed so that it can be displayed easily to users (users). To produce valid and appropriate data, then you need to pay attention to these three factors. First, the data must be relevant or on target (relevance). Second, timeliness and efficiency. And the third is on target or accurate (accurate).

When all these factors have been fulfilled properly, then the goal of Information System implementation for your business and business will produce maximum and optimal output. Information systems are an integral part of creating business processes in today's industrial era 5.0. So, you need to make sure every aspect and need to build a business is in accordance with the resources you have. So, you can make the final decision appropriately and not hastily.

System design is the process of implementing the results of system analysis into a new system design. System design is a specification or embodiment of a computer-based technical solution for business needs identified in the analysis system.

V. REFERENCES

- [1] Berry Yulianda, Ratri Fradinda Wulan, "Perancangan Sistem Informasi Pengendalian Kualitas pada Laboratorium Proses IV PT X," JOSI, vol. 17, no. 2, pp. 113-125, okt. 2018, DOI: 10.25077/josi.v17.n2.p113-125.2018.
- [2] Dina Rahmayanti, Ringgo Afrinando. "Perancangan Sistem Informasi Pada Bagian Gudang Pt. Pn Vi Unit Usaha Ophir". Jurnal Optimasi Sistem Industri, Vol. 12 No. 2, Oktber 2016:420- 426. ISSN 2088-4842.
- [3] Difana Meilani, Riyan Amirulfiras. "Perancangan Sistem Penunjang Keputusan Investasi Daerah Berbasis Web Gis Di Provinsi Sumatera Barat (Studi Kasus Badan Koordinasi Penanaman Modal Provinsi Sumatera Barat)". Jurnal Optimasi Sistem Industri, Vol. 14 No. 1, April 2016: 156-175. ISSN 2088-4842 / 2442-8795.
- [4] Yudo Purnomo et al. "Perancangan Sistem Manajemen Mutu Terintegrasi di Baristand Industri Padang". JURNAL OPTIMASI SISTEM INDUSTRI - VOL. 16 NO. 2 (2017) 80-88. <https://doi.org/10.25077/josi.v16.n2.p80-88.2017>.
- [5] Hery Hamdi Azwir, Oktavia Patriani. "Perbaikan Pengelolaan Pergudangan Melalui Penerapan Sistem Informasi Pergudangan di CV. ABB" JURNAL OPTIMASI SISTEM INDUSTRI - VOL. 16 NO. 1 (2017) 10-24. <https://doi.org/10.25077/josi.v16.n1.p10-24.2017>.